

Mechanical and Thermo-Physical Behavior of a Coated Fiber Composite

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ABSTRACT

Our recent analytical models to predict the thermo-mechanical properties of a coated short fiber composite were reviewed. Then the effect of various parameters on thermo-mechanical properties, thermal stress, and effective thermal conductivity of the coated fiber composite was discussed based on the numerical results, followed by the discussion on new applications of a coated fiber composite. It was shown through the discussion that the addition of the coating on fiber was quite effective to control the mechanical and thermo-physical properties of the composite.

THERMO-MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR

Coated fibers have been used in several types of composites, where the coating layer in composite can be expected to play various roles to improve the overall behavior of composites. Thus, the development of analytical methods to study the mechanical thermo-physical behavior of a coated fiber composite has been urgently sought. The first attempt to model a coated fiber composite was made by Walpole [1]. The Walpole model assumes that the thickness of coating on fiber is extremely thin and used the Hill-Walpole discontinuity condition [2] to derive the formula for the stress field in the extremely thin coating. Though the Walpole model provides a simple analytical tool for calculation of the stress in a coating, it suffers from a major drawback, i.e., the coating being extremely thin. In order to solve the case of coating with finite

thickness, the classical stress function method seems to be one of the few available methods. Thus, we have recently employed the classical method of separation of variables in the prolate spheroidal coordinates [3,4]. Their analytical model is based on confocal double ellipsoids as shown in Fig. 1 where a coated fiber is embedded in the infinite matrix, which is subjected to thermo-mechanical loading. In order to obtain explicit expression of the solution, we used the Bussinesq-Sadowsky stress functions [5] which are expressed by infinite series of the Legendre functions. Obviously, the solution procedure is rigorous and the convergence of the infinite series is rather slow. After having found that the model based on the stress functions is not easy to use, we have then returned to the utilization of the Eshelby theory. Based on the numerical results of Mikata and Taya [3] in that the stress field in the fiber domain is nearly constant, we have introduced the following three assumptions:

- (1) Constant stress in the fiber
- (2) Constant stress in the coating to the direction of the thickness
- (3) The coating thickness is uniform and reasonably small

Then, using the equivalency condition between an actual coated fiber and the corresponding imaginary equivalent inclusion [7] and the discontinuous condition of the stress across the interface [2], we have arrived at a closed form solution for steady-state thermal stresses subjected to the uniform temperature change [6] and to the uniform heat flux at the far field [8]. One of the advantages of this model over the Walpole's solution [1] is that this solution can account for the three-way interaction between the matrix, coating, and fiber, whereas the Walpole model includes only that between fiber and matrix. Thus, our solution is applicable to the coated fiber with reasonably thin coating with finite thickness. This difference between our model and the Walpole model is clearly shown in Fig. 2 where the normal stress at the equator of the coating region is focused for the case of continuous-coated fiber, where the exact solution is available for comparison [9]. In the figure, the abscissa stands for the ratio of the coating thickness w and fiber radius r and σ_0 is the normalization constant defined by $\sigma_0 = E_m \alpha_m \Delta T$, where E_m and α_m are the Young's modulus and coefficient of thermal

expansion of the matrix, respectively. Although the comparison of the stress in the coating was made by focusing only on a point just outside of the fiber, this point is obviously the most important location because the largest stress in the coating is expected to occur there. Another advantage in our model is that it can predict the stress field in the coated fiber composites with high fiber volume fraction. Thus, by the use of our model, we can predict the effective thermal expansion coefficient and elastic moduli as well as the thermal stress for a coated fiber composite based on the standard Eshelby method [7,10]. It should be noted, however, in our model [6,8] that the stress field in and around a coated short fiber in a composite is approximate since use of the average stress disturbance proposed by Mori and Tanaka [10] has an obvious limitation to the calculation of local stress field, but it has advantages for the estimate of the overall properties of a composite. From the practical point of view, the application of our model to thermal stress analysis is most useful for high temperature composites, such as metal matrix and ceramic matrix composites. For such high temperature composites will often experience severe thermal environment. As a demonstration, the numerical results of the stress field at the equator in a coated short fiber composite subjected to uniform temperature change ΔT are plotted as a function of the fiber-matrix stiffness ratio E_f/E_m in Fig. 3. For convenience, the local cylindrical coordinates (r, θ, z) are used where z axis was taken along the axis of the coated fiber, and σ_r , σ_θ and σ_z denote the normal stress in the coating along the radial, circumferential, and axial directions, respectively. In the figure, E, α , and ν denote the Young's modulus, coefficient of thermal expansion, and Poisson's ratio, respectively, and subscripts m, c , and f refer to the matrix, coating, and fiber phase, respectively, and w/a is the ratio of the coating thickness to radius of a short fiber. It should be noted in Fig. 3 that solid curves denote the results for volume fraction of fiber (f_1) being zero, thus, represent the Walpole's solutions and dashed curves represent the case of practically important coated short fiber composite, i.e., for finite volume fraction, $f_1 = 0.3$

Unlike the thermal stress field discussed in the previous section, the temperature field in a coated fiber composite is given by a simple closed form [11]. The corresponding analytical model is shown in Fig. 1 where the far field boundary condition is given by uniform heat flux. We

have obtained the exact solution to the temperature field for a single coated short fiber embedded in an infinite matrix that is expressed by only the associate Legendre function of the first order. Then, this solution for a single coated short fiber composite can be extended to that for a multiple fiber composite by utilizing Mori-Tanaka's smearing out method [10]. Thus, this model [11] can easily predict the effective thermal conductivity K_{ij} of an aligned coated short fiber composite with finite fiber volume fractions (f). Typical numerical results based on the above formulation are presented in Fig. 4, where the effective thermal conductivity of a coated short fiber (aspect ratio $a/c = 10$) in the aligned direction K_{33} is shown as a function of fiber volume fraction f . In the figure, the thermal conductivity of the matrix, coating, and fiber are denoted by K_m , K_c , and K_f , respectively, and the coating thickness, the larger and smaller semiaxes of the outer ellipsoid by w , c , and a , respectively. In the same figure, the results of non-coated fiber composite are also shown by a dashed line. It follows from Fig. 4 that the conductivity of the composite K_{33} increases with K_c . This suggests that the usage of highly conductive thin layer ($w/a = 0.1$) is quite effective in enhancing the overall conductivity of the composite. We also have confirmed that usage of highly resistive coating is effective to lower the overall conductivity. Similar results have recently been reported by Hasselman et al. [12]. Next, the effect of the aspect ratio of fiber c/a is shown in Fig. 5 in which K_{33}/K_m is plotted as a function of c/a for two different volume fractions of coated fiber, $f = 0.2$ and 0.4 . It is obvious from the figure that the coating on fiber becomes effective for the larger fiber aspect ratios.

NEW APPLICATIONS

Despite the concept of a coated fiber composite being relatively new, the rapid progress in the development of components for aerospace structures and electronic and electrical packaging has promoted usage of coated fiber composites. Here some of these new applications that we are currently developing will be briefly discussed; namely, magnetic behavior of a coated fiber composite, and debonded interfaces.

The first application is to control the orientation of short fibers, which is one of the most important processing problems that challenge the

composite processing industries. We have recently proposed an analytical model by which the time required for aligning short fibers suspended in a fluid subjected to an appropriate magnetic moment can be estimated [13]. This model was constructed based on our previous model for steady state heat conduction [11]. The construction of the present model was straightforward owing to the analogy of variables between thermal conductivity and permeability; i.e., temperature (magnetic potential), heat flux (magnetic flux density), and conductivity (permeability) [14]. Based on this model, torque T and time required for aligning an inclined short fiber are estimated and the results are plotted as a function of applied magnet field H^0 where μ_i and η are the permeability of the i -th phase ($i = f, m$ and c denote fiber, matrix, and coating), and the viscosity of the matrix, respectively, and the coated fiber used in this study is Ni-coated graphite fiber.

The matrix-fiber interface is known to play an important role in the thermo-mechanical behavior of a composite. Most of the damages reported on composites subjected to severe environments are associated with the micro-damage in and around the interface, which is often termed] "interface damage." Typical interface damages are debonding and cavitation at the interfaces. The above interface damages can be modelled as a special case of a coated fiber composite. Namely, the damaged zone along the interface can be treated as a coating with weak mechanical properties. We are currently investigation the overall mechanical behavior of a composite with damaged interfaces [15]. Similar problems have been studied in a different manner by Mura and his co-workers [16], Wakashima and his co-workers [17,18], and Hasselman et al. [12], although their models are different from the concept of a coated fiber composite.

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REFERENCES

1. Walpole, L.J., A coated inclusion in an elastic medium. Math. Proc. Camb. Phil. Soc., 1978, 83, 495-506.
2. Hill, R., Discontinuity relations in mechanics of solids. Progress in Solid Mechanics, 2, eds. I.N. Sneddon and R. Hill, North-Holland, Amsterdam, 1961, 245-276.
3. Mikata, Y., and Taya, M., Stress field in and around a coated short fiber in an infinite matrix subjected to uniaxial and biaxial loadings. J. Appl. Mech., 48, 1985, 19-24.
4. Mikata, Y., and Taya, M., Thermal stresses in a coated short fiber composite, J. Appl. Mech., 53, 1986, 681-689.
5. Sadowsky, M.A., and Sternberg, E., Stress concentration around an ellipsoidal cavity in an infinite body under arbitrary plane stress perpendicular to the axis of revolution of cavity, J. Appl. Mech., Sept. 1947, A-191-201.
6. Hatta, H., and Taya, M., Thermal stress in a coated short fiber composite. ASME J. Eng. Mater. Tech.
7. Eshelby, J.D., The determination of the elastic field of an ellipsoidal inclusion, and related problems. Proc. Roy. Soc. A241, 1957, 376-396.
8. Hatta, H., and Taya, M., Thermal stress in a coated short fiber composite. Composite '86: Recent Advances in Japan and the United States, Proc. 3rd Japan-US Conf. Composite Mater. eds. K. Kawata, S. Umekawa, and A. Kobayashi, 1986, 179-186.
9. Mikata, Y., and Taya, M., Stress field in a coated continuous fiber composite subjected to thermo-mechanical loadings. J. Composite Materials, 19, 1985, 554-578.
10. Mori, T., and Tanaka, K., Average stress in matrix and average energy of materials with misfitting inclusion, Act. Met., 21, 1973, 571-574.
11. Hatta, H., and Taya, M., Thermal conductivity of coated filler composites. J. Appl. Phys., 59, 1986, 1851-60.
12. Hasselman, D.P.H., and Johnson, L.F., Effective Thermal Conductivity of Composites with Interfacial Thermal Barrier Resistance, J. Comp. Mater., in press.
13. Hatta, H., and Yamashita, S., Fiber orientation control by means of magnetic moment. submitted for publication.
14. Ashton, J.E., Halpin, J.C., and Petit, P.H., Primer on Composite Materials: Analysis, Technomic, Lancaster USA, 1969.
15. Taya, M. unpublished work.

16. Mura, T., Jasiuk, I., and Tsuchida, E., "The stress Field of Sliding Inclusion," *Intl. J. Solids Structs*, 21, 1985, 1165-1179.
17. Yoda, S., Kurihara, N., Wakashima, K., and Umekawa, S., "Thermal Cycling-Induced Deformation of Fibrous Composites with Particular Reference to the Tungsten-Copper System" *Metal Trans.*, 9A, 1978, 1229-1236.
18. Wakashima, K., Choi, B.H., and Lee, S.H., "Temperature Cycling-Induced Superplasticity in Metal Matrix Composites," *Proc. 3rd Japan-US Conf. Comp. Mater.*, eds. Kawataik, Umekawa, S., and Kobayashi, A., Japan Soc. Comp. Mater., in press.

Figure 1. Analytical model for a coated short composite.

Figure 2. Comparison of the stress in the coating region predicted by various models.

Figure 3. Thermal stresses at equator in the coating vs. fiber-matrix stiffness ratio.

Figure 4. Effect of coating on the thermal conductivity of a coated fiber composite.

Figure 5. Effect of fiber aspect ratio on the thermal conductivity of a coated fiber composite.

Figure 6. Magnetic torque T and time required for rotation t vs. intensity of applied magnetic field H^0 .